

DIGITAL EDUCATION: A GATEWAY FOR INCLUSIVE PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract

The digital education is one of the most potentially emerging routes for learning especially for the children with special needs. By using digital technology one can improve the learning at all levels, and for people of all backgrounds. Digital education is the educational resources for the differently able students. The current paper will review the development of education provision for children with special educational needs in India and the factors which have influenced current policy drive to Inclusive education supported by assistive technologies. Digital Education represents a new model for inclusive Educational which can bring benefits to both children with special needs and their non-disabled peers. Present paper will also reflect on the gap between the model of Inclusive Education that is being striven for and the current model of provision and the critical contribution that Information and communication Technology or Assistive Technology can make as a means for bridging that gap. Its aim is to encourage thinking and discussion about the future direction for the development of an inclusive education model in direct response to needs, but which would contain principles and elements that could be applied to any developing country context.

Key Words: Digital education, children with special needs, inclusive Education

Introduction

Inclusion is an enlightening philosophy that fetches all categories of students together to construct a class or school atmosphere that is based on reception, belonging and admiration for human diversity. Effective inclusion creates a cooperative, caring and developing community of students which is based on providing all pupils the amenities and accommodations they need to learn. The awareness of inclusive training is gaining ground all over the world. The elementary philosophy behind inclusion is that 'children, who learn together, learn to live together' It is a novel method to access to a mutual education for all children, with admittance to a curriculum suitable for all learners. This is an approach where all children irrespective of their abilities, backgrounds, awareness or disabilities are self-confessed to have an education system which admits the proprietorship of any kind an education system accepting the ownership of any kind of diversity and the principle that the aim of education should be to include all children. In this regard the Indian constitution ensures the right to educations for all

disabled children with 86th amendment in the constitution. The perception and philosophy of inclusive education gained remarkable international exchange when the United Nations endorsed the awareness of 'Education for all' in a conference at Thailand in 1990. A declaration of program on inclusive education emanating from the 1994 Salamanca conference tossed an enormous challenge to all nations, schools and educators to real education for all students together with those with special needs. Post to Salamanca conference, inclusive education has become a regularly used notion in the international literature and has been rendered fairness though various international declarations.

All children with disability have a right to education. In the past decade, education of children with disabilities has seen a paradigm shift from segregated education in separate schools to inclusive education in regular schools along with normal children. Inclusive education means all students are welcome regardless of differences. It is a globally accepted as the best to ensure the right to education for all. Inclusive education is an ideology .It is concept of effective school where every child has a place to study and teachers' facilitators of learning. India is the country of rural area. More than 90% of disabled students are found in rural area in India (Mani, 2003). Digital education are all over the place and they're bringing a lot of stimulating opportunities for elementary school students, impacting what, where and how education is delivered. For this reason, supporting schools to make the most of new technologies is a significant part of the Ministry's work programme. All schools will have access to the technology available to provide, high capacity, high quality, internet access for teaching and learning. Connected classrooms offer today's students and teachers easier, reasonable, and more rapidly right to use to information, teaching and learning resources, peers, experts and the wider society. Article 7 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with disabilities obliges States Parties to take all necessary measures to ensure the full enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by children with disabilities on an equal basis with other children. In addition, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with disabilities in several other articles also recognizes the importance of access to assistive technology and urges Member States to ensure its availability at an affordable cost. Assistive technology has been found to be the first step for any next steps: for a child with a disability to play with other children; go to school and be educated; and to become a successful citizen and contributing member of society.

According to the convention on the Rights of Persons with disabilities, children with disabilities includes children "who have mental, physical, intellectual or sensory impairments as represented by schematic shown in Fig. 1. Depending on the definition and measure of disability, estimates of the prevalence of children with disabilities. The common impairments include blindness, Down syndrome, brain injury, cerebral palsy, autism, congenital anomalies, hearing loss, intellectual and learning disabilities, muscular dystrophy, traumatic spinal cord injury, speech impairments and visual loss. The Convention on the Rights of Persons with

Disabilities calls for measures to address disability at different levels: health services; habilitation and rehabilitation services; assistive technology services; and accessibility. For example, clubfoot may be corrected surgically; through physiotherapy; or through the use of a foot orthosis. If clubfoot is not treated successfully, long-term use of a wheelchair may be needed (Fig. 2). Other impairments require other types of assistive technology for example a hearing aid (Fig. 3) or low-vision glasses to overcome their functional impairments as shown in (Fig. 4).

Fig 1: Schematic showing different categories of differently able students

Fig 2: Different modes of mobility of disabled candidates

Fig 3: Different tools used for hearing

Fig 4: Various tool used by disabled candidates weak in vision

According to The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health defines assistive products and technology as any product, instrument, equipment or technology adapted or specially designed for improving the functioning of a person with a disability 5 The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) defines assistive products more broadly as any product, especially produced or generally available, that is used by or for persons with disability: for participation; to protect, support, train, measure or substitute for body

functions/structures and activities; or to prevent impairments, activity limitations or participation restrictions. This includes devices, equipment, instruments and software.

Connecting with technology

Drastic improvements in the inclusive education have been noticed with the advancement in the field of information technology especially the telecommunication. Students and differently able students are using digital devices like laptops and tablets to rapidly, easily and efficiently connect with a massive and ever-growing number of educational tools and assets and subject-matter experts over the internet. Teachers are using online networks and social media to connect with several schools and peers who can help them adapt their teaching practices to make the most of digital tools. Students are using digital technologies to connect with other students across the country and across the world, and to engage in self-directed learning in areas of personal interest and expertise. Parents are forming stronger connections with schools using digital services like social networks, websites and online surveys.

The “Digital Education” is one of the best usages of telecommunication toward inclusive education. It facilitates learning of students including differently able students by the usage of communication technology. The advantages of having computer-assisted training in the tutorial room are that the computer can assist as an instructor. Tutors can only aid pupils in the learning process to a certain level. The digital technology allows the pupil to continue their educations at home and can act as a tutor for the students who are falling behind especially the disabled candidates. This novel technology also allows students to advance at their own pace as they learn. Another advantage of new technology (such as the smart board, ipads, electronic readers, dictionaries etc.) information can be presented in such a large variety of ways (orally, visually, differently sized fonts, different colors, etc.) that almost any type of learner can benefit and learn through the new technologies. The internet and other forms of knowledge give students access to a huge fortune of knowledge that earlier was not as available to students. Productivity is an enormous benefit from having technology in the classrooms. Instructors and pupils alike can rapidly access vast amounts of information and present in through a variety of mediums. Another benefit that people argue is that technology, especially the internet, permits for equality within education. The information and the technology that students use are available for everyone, they just have to go get it. Of course, this is referring more to the use of the internet because certain educational technologies are too expensive for less fortunate people to afford access to. The digital education has advantages in domain of time, place, pace, instruction. Fig. 5 shows the usefulness of digital education in different dimensions. Using it the learning is no longer limited to the school day or the school year. The Internet and a propagation of Internet access devices have given students the ability to learn anytime. Moreover, learning is no longer restricted within the walls of a classroom. The Internet and a proliferation of Internet access devices have given students the ability to learn anywhere and everywhere. It is no longer restricted to the instruction used by the teacher. Communicating and adaptive software allows students to learn in their own style, making learning personal and

engaging. New learning technologies provide real time data that gives teachers the information they need to adjust instruction to meet the unique needs of each student. Learning is no longer restricted to the pace of an entire classroom of students. Interactive and adaptive software allows students to learn at their own pace, spending more or less time on lessons or subjects to achieve the same level of learning.

Digital learning is more than just providing students with a laptop. It requires a combination of technology, digital content and instruction. Technology facilitates how students receive content. It includes Internet access and hardware, which can be any Internet access device – from a desktop to a laptop to an iPad to a smart phone. Technology is the tool, not the instruction. It provides digital content that is the high quality educational material which is delivered through technology. It ranges from novel attractive, interactive and adaptive software to classic literature to video lectures to games. It isn't simply a PDF of text or a PowerPoint presentation. Though the usage of digital technology helps the student both the normal and disabled in learning, but the tutors are essential for the usage of digital learning. Technology may change the role of the teacher but it will never eliminate the need for a teacher. With digital learning, teachers will be able to provide the personalized guidance and assistance to ensure students learn and stay on track – throughout the year and year after year – to graduate from high school. Teachers may be the guide on the side, not the sage on the stage.

Fig.5 Schematic showing the role of digital education in different dimensions of life

Supporting schools to be successful

Schools and their communities to ensure they have access to modern technology and that teachers and principals can use their high quality internet connections. The digital Education is transform training and learning in our schools. Digital Education is full advantage of this opportunity to help our schools become world leaders in digital education systems through changes to their infrastructure, practices and pedagogy.

Impact of digital education in the inclusive classroom

The impact that technology has had on today's schools has been moderately significant. This widespread adoption of technology has completely changed how teachers educate and students study. Teachers are learning how to teach with technologies such as computers, iPads, Smart Boards, tablets, digital cameras,) while students are using latest technology to shape how they be trained. By embracing and integrating technology in the classroom, we are setting our

students up for a successful life outside of school. Here are a few benefits of using it. Technology occupies an important place within students' lives. When they are not in school, just about everything that they do is connected in some way to technology. By integrating technology into the classroom, teachers are changing the way they used to teach (lectures six hours a day) and providing student s with the tools that will take them into the 21st century. Technology changes by the minute, and as educators we need to keep up with the times in order to best prepare our students for this ever-changing world that we live in. While we just saw how integrating technology into the classroom has its benefits, it's important to note that traditional learning processes are just as essential. Take time to learn about each element of ed-tech that you will incorporate into your classroom. When you do, you will find that technology can have a profound impact on your students learning.

Conclusion

The digital education is one of the most powerful emerging routes for learning especially for differently able students. By using such technology we can improve the learning at all levels, in every domain and for people of all backgrounds. Digital education is the educational resources for the differently able students. Even now a day's majority of the schools are using digital tools like tablets, laptop. School Administration provides Wi-Fi connection to students and teachers. Teachers are using online networks and social media and engage in self-directed learning in area of personal interest and expertise. By the end of 2016 majority of school will have access to the digital education which will provide high quality, capacity and fast internet access for teaching and learning?

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